

Monitoring Climate Change in Cultural Heritage Sites Through Enhanced Visualisation Experiences and Crowdsourcing

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One of the most significant consequences of climate change is the threat it poses to cultural heritage sites. The TRIQUETRA project addresses this critical challenge by applying a comprehensive risk assessment framework. This framework integrates both traditional and advanced technologies, including remote sensing and laser-based spectroscopy, to quantify the severity of risks, monitor their progression, and inform effective mitigation strategies.

Climate risks emerge from the interplay of climate hazards, exposure, and vulnerability. Understanding these risks at the site level is essential to ensure the implementation of appropriate adaptation and mitigation measures. Recent research highlights the compounded impacts of climate-induced geo-hazards, such as landslides and earthquakes, which threaten the physical integrity of monuments and the socio-economic systems they support.

Citizen engagement is a core component of the TRIQUETRA project, which includes a dynamic web and mobile platform where visitors actively participate in monitoring cultural heritage sites. The TRIQUETRA application enables citizens and visitors to contribute valuable datasets by capturing and uploading site photos, complementing and enhancing existing 3D models. A backend system assists cultural site authorities in better monitoring sites by providing up-to-date imagery and reports from visitors. Simultaneously, the TRIQUETRA Citizen Engagement Application creates an interactive and enriched experience for visitors through Virtual Reality (VR) and immersive Augmented Reality (AR) technologies. The application offers additional information through VR and AR experiences, allowing users to learn more about critical features at risk, such as areas affected by climate change or structural vulnerabilities. This fosters awareness and encourages preservation efforts.

The Choirokoitia case study demonstrates the application of the TRIQUETRA methodology in monitoring how the site is affected by climate change while also enhancing the visitor experience. Choirokoitia, a UNESCO World Heritage Site, is one of the best-preserved Neolithic sites in the Mediterranean. It represents the Aceramic Neolithic period of Cyprus at its peak, around the beginning of the 9th millennium BCE. Located in the District of Larnaka, about 6 km from the southern coast of Cyprus, the site leverages crowd-sourced information to provide stakeholders with real-time updates on its condition. By comparing uploaded images to a referenced 3D model, authorities gain valuable insights for preservation.

By integrating advanced technologies and community-driven monitoring, TRIQUETRA ensures a holistic approach to safeguarding cultural heritage. The project establishes a replicable framework that enhances risk assessment and promotes active participation in preservation efforts, offering scalable benefits for cultural heritage sites worldwide.